

Third-Party Fund (DPK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

Umar Abdillah Abidin, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang

wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

ABSTRACT. This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Third Party Fund (TPF) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the TPF ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the TPF ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the TPF ratio using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 628 journal publications regarding the TPF ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the TPF ratio are divided into 6 clusters and 190 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 5 topics around the TPF ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around TPF ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Third Party Fund (TPF); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic & Conventional Banking

Introduction

Banking plays a very important role in economic activities because banking has many functions and tasks that are very important in supporting economic growth and development. Banking also plays an important role in financing investment and helping to drive economic growth through financing business projects. Banking also plays an important role in maintaining financial system stability and maintaining public confidence in the financial system. Large banks have a very important role in maintaining financial system stability by implementing good risk management practices and by having sufficient reserve funds to overcome financial crisis situations. Banking plays a role as financial intermediation, namely bridging parties who have excess funds (for example companies or individuals) with parties who need funds (such as other companies or individuals), which are called third party funds. Third Party Funds (DPK) are funds managed by banks or other financial companies which do not include customer funds or the bank's own funds. DPK is considered an alternative source of funds for banks and other financial companies, so it can be used to expand their funding base. DPK can also be used by banks to increase their liquidity and strengthen their financial position. However, like other sources of funds, TPF also has risks that need to be considered by banks and financial companies that manage them.

Pratiwi (2020) conducted research that provides empirical evidence about the influence of DPK (Third Party Funds) and interest rates on profitability (ROA) at PT. Bank Mega Tbk. Both have significant influence. DPK is funds deposited by customers with the bank and can be used by the bank to distribute credit. The greater the available DPK, the greater the amount of credit that can be disbursed by the bank,

which means the greater the interest income received by the bank. Therefore, the greater the DPK, the higher the bank's ROA. Meanwhile, the interest rate is the interest rate received by the bank from customers who deposit funds with the bank, and also the interest rate paid by the bank to customers who borrow funds. If the interest rate received by the bank is higher than the interest rate paid, then the bank's profitability will increase, and vice versa. Therefore, the higher the interest rate, the higher the bank's ROA. Habibah (2021) conducted research aimed at showing and describing the influence of gross domestic product and inflation on TPF partially and simultaneously. Both have a significant influence on banking deposits (DPK) in an economy. GDP is a measure of a country's overall economic output, and an increase in GDP is usually considered a sign of positive economic growth. If GDP increases, consumer and business confidence will increase, and they will tend to keep more money in banks as deposits. This will increase the number of TPF. Inflation is a general increase in prices in the economy, and can affect TPF because it affects the value of money saved. If the inflation rate is high, the value of money will tend to fall, so people tend to look for better investment alternatives such as bonds or shares. This can reduce the number of TPF. However, if the inflation rate is low and stable, then people tend to trust banks more and are more likely to keep their money as deposits, which will increase the amount of deposits. Maulidha (2022) researched the DPK with the aim of testing the influence of the DPK and governance good corporate governance on the performance of sharia banks from a customer perspective. The results of this research are that DPK (Third Party Funds) is a source of funding for Islamic banks. DPK itself is funds collected from customers and used by sharia banks to finance their business activities. Therefore, good governance in Islamic banks is very important to ensure that customer funds can be utilized optimally and their security is guaranteed. Good corporate governance also has a huge influence on the performance of Islamic banks from a customer perspective. Good governance will ensure that Islamic banks can manage their resources and operations efficiently, transparently and accountably. This will increase customer confidence in Islamic banks and help build a positive image for Islamic banks.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding TPF in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding DPK. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research the DPK. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the TPF ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Third Party Funds (DPK) are funds deposited by customers with banks and used by banks as a source of funding to carry out business activities, such as providing credit. DPK has a different nature from savings or deposits, because DPK does not have the right to withdraw funds and does not have collateral from the bank. Banks can use these funds in accordance with applicable policies and regulations. However, even though TPF does not have a guarantee from the bank, banks usually have an obligation to maintain the security and smoothness of customer funds held as DPK.

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and

informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature. Some applications of bibliometric studies include citation network analysis, cluster analysis, and visibility analysis. The results of bibliometric studies can be used by researchers, government and industry to understand developments and contributions in the field of science and to determine future research directions.

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer can help researchers and analysts carry out citation network analysis, find relationships between scientific fields, and understand trends and issues in scientific literature. It also helps in determining future research directions and gaining insight into the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions, and scientific fields. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently.

Library Research is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions. Library Research studies are usually conducted as part of the research process to ensure that researchers understand the existing research environment and produce non-duplicative results. It also helps in determining problems and gaps in the existing literature and helps in the formulation of hypotheses and understanding of specific research areas. Library Research studies can be carried out by accessing scientific publication databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Researchers can also carry out manual searches through scientific journals and related books. Library Research studies must be carried out with a systematic and objective methodology to ensure that the results are accurate and valid.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Third Party Funds (DPK). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on DPK in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words "Third Party Funds" and "DPK" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding DPK using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on

publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around DPK using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around DPK using a Library Research study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications regarding Third Party Funds (DPK) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Table 1 shows the results of searches for scientific publications on Third Party Funds carried out in the period 2007 to 2022. The search results show an increase in the number of publications, especially in certain years. For example, in 2012, there was an increase in the first publication, namely from 3 articles to 14 articles. In the following years, the number of publications continued to increase until in 2017 it reached 80 articles. Even though there was a decline in 2018, in 2021 publications increased again rapidly to 103 articles.

Table 1. Article publication data regarding Third Party Funds by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publications	Year of Publication	Number of Publications	Year of Publication	Number of Publications
2007	1	2013	26	2018	61
2009	4	2014	31	2019	69
2010	5	2015	48	2020	90
2011	3	2016	46	2021	103
2012	14	2017	80	2022	47

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016

Table 2 shows that the most affiliated publishers of research articles on third party funds are JIMAT (Accounting Student Scientific Journal) Undiksha and FEB Student Scientific Journal, each with 20 articles published.

Table 2. Data ranking list of names of affiliates of article publishers regarding Third Party Funds

Affiliate Name	Number of Publications
JIMAT (Accounting Student Scientific Journal) Undiksha & FEB Student Scientific Journal	20
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics & Journal of Development and Equity	13
Accounting E-Journal & Warmadewa Economic Development Journal (WEDJ)	10
Management E-Journal	9
Students Journal of Accounting and Banking	8
Diponegoro Journal of Management, Journal of Development Economics, Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Economics, Owner: Research and Accounting Journal	6
ACCURATE UNIBBA FE Accounting Scientific Journal, Efficiency Scientific Periodical Journal, Accounting Economics Student Scientific Journal, Masharif al-Syariah Journal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Journal of Accounting and Business Research	5
AT-TAWASSUTH: Journal of Islamic Economics, E-JRM: Electronic Journal of Management Research, Falah: Journal of Sharia	4

Economics, Accounting Journal, Economic Journal, EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research., Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, Maps Journal (Sharia Banking Management), Students' Journal of Accounting and Banking

Accountability, AL-MASHARIF: JOURNAL OF ECONOMIC AND ISLAMIC SCIENCE, Al-Sharf: Journal of Islamic Economics, An-Nisbah: Journal of Sharia Economics, ARTHA SATYA DHARMA, Bisma: Journal of Management, e_Scientific Journal of Accounting Research, e-Journal of Industrial and Monetary Trade, Economics and Business, Eqien - Journal of Economics and Business, Indonesian Journal of Economics and Management, Jesya (Journal of Economics and Sharia Economics), Journal of Financial Economics & Investment, Jurnal Akrab Juara, JOURNAL OF SHARIA ECONOMICS, Scientific Journal of Business Economics, Journal of Financial Sciences and Banking (JIKA), Journal of Management Science, Journal of Accounting Scientific Studies, Faculty of Economics, UNTAN (KIAFE), Journal of Management Update, Journal of Accounting and Financial Research, Journal of Financial and Accounting Research, JYRS: Online Journal for Students of the Faculty of Sharia and Islamic Economics Study Program, MASLAHAH (Journal of Islamic Law and Sharia Banking), Syntax Idea, Vocational: Journal of Accounting Research

3

ADVANCE, AKTSAR: Journal of Sharia Accounting, ACTUAL, ACCOUNTABLE, Al-bank: Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance, Al-Urban: Journal of Sharia Economics and Islamic Philanthropy, COMPETITIVE, Diponegoro Journal of Accounting, Economica: Journal of Islamic Economics, EKONOMIA, Ekonomis: Journal of Economics and Business, EkoPreneur, Expansion: Journal of Economics, Finance, Banking and Accounting, EQUILIBRIUM, FORUM ECONOMY, Future: Journal of Management and Accounting, Imara: JOURNAL OF ISLAMIC ECONOMIC RESEARCH, J-EBIS (Journal of Islamic Economics and Business), Journal of Accounting and Investment, Journal of Applied Islamic Economics and Finance, Journal of Business & Banking, JPS (Jurnal of Sharia Banking), JURIS (Shariah Scientific Journal), JOURNAL OF ADMINISTRATION AND PUBLIC POLICY, Journal of Accounting AKUNESA, Journal of Accounting and Technology Systems Information, BUSINESS & ENTREPRENEURSHIP Journal, Curvanomic Journal, Economic Journal of Accounting and Management, JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING ECONOMICS, Journal of Corporate Economics, Journal of Sharia Economics, Accounting and Banking (JESKaPe), Scientific Journal of Accounting and Humanics, Scientific Journal of Unitary Management, MEA Scientific Journal (Management, Economics & Accounting), Journal of Investment, Journal of Finance and Banking, Journal of Business Management, Journal of Media Accounting (Mediation), Journal of Media Wahana Ekonomika, Journal of Muara Ilmu Economics and Business, Journal of Economic Education Undiksha, JOURNAL OF SOCIAL HUMANITY EDUCATION RESEARCH, REKSA Journal: Financial, Sharia and Audit Engineering, Malahayati Accounting and Management Research Journal, Management Research Journal Widya Wiwaha College of

2

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around DPK

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software

co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Third Party Funds divided into 6 clusters and 190 topics, such as there is picture 1 below.

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 71 topics, namely: amount, analysis technique, bank, Indonesian bank, sharia commercial bank, banking, BPRS, bus, credit, customer, data analysis, December, deposit, development, distribution, economic growth, exchange rate, factor, bank, financial services authority, form, fund, gdp, gross domestic product, growth, impact, Indonesia, inflation, influence, interest rate, Islamic bank, Islamic banking, Islamic commercial bank, Jakarta, January, level, model, mudharabah financing, negative effect, number, object, office, official website, ojk, order, performance, person, positive effect, profit, profit sharing, promotion cost, public, quantitative approach, rate, relationship, research, research method, role, saving, secondary data, service, sharia bank, sharia commercial bank, significant influence, study, sharia bank, third party fund, time deposit, tpf, variable, year.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 51 topics, namely: analysis of the influence of third party funds, independent banks, Indonesian state banks, Indonesian people's banks, bi rates, Indonesian stock exchange, capital adequacy ratio, car, credit distribution, and third party funds, third party funds, data, data analysis technique, deposit ratio, documentation, dpk, finance, the results of this research show, the results of the research show, Indonesia period, inflation, keywords, capital adequacy, keywords, credit, ldr, loan, lpd, method, net interest margin, nim, non-performing loan, npl, on, this research, this research aims, influence, influence of third party funds, performing loan, period, company, purposive sampling, sample, spss, year, tbk, data analysis techniques, third party, test, t test.
- Cluster 3. The dark blue color consists of 40 topics, namely: analysis, analysis method, asset, banking company, bopo, bpr, capital adequacy, coefficient, commercial bank, company, cost, credit risk, determination, effect, expemse, financial performance, financial statement, hypothesis testing, idx, income, independent variable, Indonesia stock exchange, insignificant effect, keyword, lending, multiple linear regression analysis, operating income, period, population, profitability, purposive sampling method, roa, roe, sample, sampling technique, significant level, significant negative effect, significant positive effect, technique.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 20 topics, namely: independent sharia bank, classic assumption test, classical assumption test, equity, f test, fdr, financial report, financing, liquidity, multiple regression analysis, murabahah, murabahah financing, non-performing financing, npf, performing financing, t test, test, total assets, type, value.
- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 4 topics, namely: investment, return, roi.
- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 4 topics, namely: capital, multiple linear regression, operational performance, significant effects.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Third Party Fund Growth Strategies in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Based on several studies, there are 6 strategies used by banks to grow Third Party Funds in Sharia and Conventional Banking from the community, namely:

The first strategy, with the TOWS Matrix approach. That is a tool used in SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats). TOWS Matrix combines SWOT analysis by creating strategies related to a company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. This allows companies to evaluate their current position and develop strategies to achieve their goals. Each element of SWOT is linked to each of the other elements to create four strategy categories: SO (Strength-Opportunities), ST (Strength-Threats), WO (Weaknesses-Opportunities), and WT (Weaknesses-Threats).

The second strategy, with the SPACE Matrix approach. This is one of the tools used in strategic analysis which is used to evaluate a company's position in the market environment. This allows the company to evaluate the level of stability and growth rate of the market and make decisions about how the company should compete in that market. The SPACE Matrix is built based on two main dimensions that influence company strategy, namely the level of industry stability and the level of market growth. The level of industry stability is measured using factors such as competitive intensity, level of industry concentration, and regulatory stability. Market growth rate is measured using factors such as market growth rate, technological advancement rate, and market share rate. After obtaining scores for both dimensions, companies can place themselves in the matrix, which is divided into four quadrants: aggressive, conservative, defensive, and combined. Each quadrant recommends a different strategy for companies to follow.

The third strategy, with the Grand Strategy Matrix approach. It is a tool used in strategic analysis that helps companies evaluate their position and develop strategies that suit the company's goals. It consists of four quadrants that indicate different levels of risk, namely: (1) Quadrant I, companies located here should pursue aggressive growth strategies, because they have a strong market position and good market growth prospects; (2) quadrant II, companies located here should pursue a stable strategy, because they have a strong market position, but poor market growth prospects; (3) quadrant III, companies located here must pursue a defensive strategy, because they have a weak market position and poor market growth prospects; (4) quadrant IV, companies located here should pursue aggressive strategies, because they have a weak market position, but good market growth prospects. Companies can place themselves in quadrants by taking into account two main dimensions, namely relative market position and market growth prospects. After finding a position in the quadrant, the company can develop a strategy that suits market conditions and company goals.

The fourth strategy, with the Greiner Curve approach. It is a model used to explain the changes that occur in an organization during a period of growth. This model was developed by Larry Greiner in 1972. This model states that as an organization grows, the company will experience several different phases, namely: (1) Creativity Phase, rapid growth with rapid development within the organization; (2) Direction Phase, steady growth with steady development in the organization; (3) Delegation Phase, slow growth with slow development in the organization; (4) Coordinator Phase, rapid growth with rapid development in the organization; (5) Collaboration Phase, stable growth with stable development in the organization; (6) Renewal Phase, slow growth with slow development in the organization. According to Greiner, companies will experience problems during the delegation phase and the Renewal phase and these problems must be resolved in order to continue stable

growth. This model is used to understand the problems that occur in organizations during periods of growth and provide approaches to overcome them. However, keep in mind that this model is only a general guideline, not a rule that must be followed and each company may experience different growth periods.

Fifth strategy, with the McKinsey approach Growth Model is a methodology used by McKinsey & Company consultants to help companies or organizations evaluate growth potential and develop action plans to pursue that growth potential. This methodology includes market analysis, consumer segmentation, identification of growth opportunities, and development of strategies to achieve expected growth. This model is used in various industries and fields to help companies increase revenue and profits through market expansion, product innovation, and operational efficiency.

The sixth strategy, with the SFAS Matrix approach. This is an analytical method used to evaluate projects or business activities by combining financial and non-financial aspects. Single Factor Assessment Sheet (SFAS) or matrix This SFAS is used to evaluate projects or activities based on several factors such as costs, benefits, risks and impacts. This matrix is used to help decision makers evaluate various alternatives and make the right decisions. SFAS itself consists of two components, namely criteria and factors. Criteria are components used to evaluate projects or business activities, while factors are aspects used in evaluating criteria. In the SFAS Matrix, the factors evaluated above are compared with each other to get a score which will be used to determine the priority of the project or activity to be carried out.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Public Interest, Record Keeping, Legal Basis and Policy on Third Party Funds in Sharia and Conventional Banking

First, the factors that influence people's interest in becoming DPK customers in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: (1) product aspects (product completeness, product quality); (2) in terms of rewards (halal rewards, competitive rewards, cheap administration); (3) location aspect (ATM facilities, easy to reach location, parking area); (4) promotion aspect (sales promotion & advertising); (5) service process aspects (standard service & friendliness); (6) aspects of the bank's image (employee morale and guaranteed investment security); (7) aspects of bank employees (Islamic morals & professionalism); (8) in terms of physical facilities (building condition and savings book complete with ATM card); (9) transparency aspect (ratio/margin offered and financial reports); and (10) aspects of social activities (collection & distribution of zakat, infaq, alms).

Second, accounting reports for Third Party Funds (DPK). Research on the system for calculating and recording DPK interest tax accounting has been carried out at Bank Sulut, Bank Mandiri in the Manado area, KSP Mandala Amerta Sedana Singaraja, BPR Suryajaya Ubud.

Third, efficient methods for collecting TPF in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: (1) Data Envelopment Analysis/DEA approach; (2) International Financial Reporting Standards/IFRS approach; (3) Hybrid Package forecast approach with R Studio Cloud at Bank Muamalat Indonesia; (4) Vector Auto Regressive/VAR and Error Correction Model/ECM approaches.

Fourth, matters relating to law, supervision and policy, namely: (1) provisions on DPK premiums by LPS at Rural Credit Banks; (2) legal protection for TPF at Bank SulutGo KC Airmadidi; (3) The role of the Sharia Supervisory Board; (4) guaranteeing Third Party Funds for term deposits at Rural Credit Banks in East Kalimantan.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Factors that Influence the Collection of Third Party Funds in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Based on several studies, there are 53 factors that influence the collection of TPF in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Social, cultural and religious activities at the Village Credit Institution/LPD, Tabanan Regency, Bali; (2) Total assets at Sharia Commercial Banks; (3) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO at IDX-registered Sharia Commercial Banks, Sharia BPRs in West Java, Conventional Commercial Banks, Bank Permata Jakarta; (4) Education and training costs at Sharia Commercial Banks; (5) BI 7-Day Repo Rate at Sharia Commercial Banks; (6) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR at Sharia BPRs in West Java and Conventional Commercial Banks; (7) Financing to Deposit Ratio at Sharia Commercial Banks and Sharia BPRs in West Java; (8) Returns/profit sharing/bonuses/returns at Sharia Commercial Banks, Sharia Business Units and BPRS; (9) Composite Stock Price Index/IHSG for Conventional Commercial Banks and Sharia Commercial Banks; (10) Community Development Index/HDI at BPD East Java; (11) Inflation at Sharia Commercial Banks, Sharia Commercial Banks in Lhokseumawe, BNI, Sharia Business Units, BPD East Java; (12) Islamic Corporate Governance/ICG at Sharia Commercial Banks; (13) Number of office networks at Sharia Commercial Banks, Bank DKI Syariah, BPRS in Indonesia; (14) Number of customer accounts with BPRS; (15) The amount of money circulating in Conventional Commercial Banks; (16) Number of residents in BPD East Java; (17) Monetary policy at Sharia Commercial Banks; (18) Capital adequacy/ratio at Rural Banks in Tangerang, Foreign Exchange Private Banks, Sharia Commercial Banks; (19) Foreign exchange rates at BNI, Sharia Commercial Bank, State Foreign Exchange Bank.

Next, namely: (20) Company performance using the Sharia Conformity and Profitability/SCnP approach; (21) Financial performance of Conventional Commercial Banks listed on the IDX; (22) Credit to government banks registered on the IDX; (23) Quality of Frontliner service at BSM KC Pondok Gede Bekasi; (24) Sharia services/office channeling (Sharia Business Unit); (25) Laku Pandai (Commercial Bank registered on the IDX); (26) Liquidity (Commercial Banks listed on the IDX use the Liquidity Reserve Requirement Ratio approach, Sharia Commercial Banks); (27) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR (Commercial Banks registered on the IDX, BTN KC Medan, BUMN Commercial Banks); (28) Macroeconomics (Sharia Commercial Bank, Indonesian Sharia Bank); (29) Retail, corporate and priority customers (Sharia Commercial Banks); (30) Net Interest Margin/NIM (BUMN Commercial Banks); (31) Non Performing Financing/NPF (BUMN Commercial Banks, Sharia BPRs in West Java); (32) Non Performing Loans/NPL (BUMN Commercial Banks); (33) Indonesian retail bonds (Conventional Commercial Banks); (34) Operations (People's Credit Bank in Tangerang); (35) Gross Domestic Product (Sharia Commercial Banks); (36) National Income (Commercial Banks); (37) Musyarakah Financing, Murabahah (Sharia People's Bank Financing); (38) Good Corporate Governance Rating (Sharia Commercial Bank); (39) Economic growth (Sharia Commercial Bank); (40) Deposit/Mudharabah/Wadiah savings products (Bank Sumut KCP Syariah Simpang Kayu Besar).

Next, namely: (41) Profitability/Return On Assets/Return On Equity (Conventional Commercial Banks, Private Foreign Exchange Banks. BPRS in Indonesia); (42) Promotion (BRI Syariah, BMT Masalahah Besuk Agung Branch, Bank Mandiri, Sharia Commercial Bank, BPRS, Bank Muamalat Indonesia KCP Binjai, Bank Permata Jakarta); (43) Profitability (Sharia Commercial Bank, Bank Muamalat Indonesia); (44) Financing risk (Sharia Commercial Bank); (45) Credit risk (Rural Bank

in Tangerang, Private Foreign Exchange Bank); (46) Situation (Covid-19 pandemic period); (47) Marketing strategy (BPRS Harta Insan Karimah Cikarang uses the Marketing Funding approach, Bank Syariah Mandiri uses the Exponential Smoothing forecasting technique approach); (48) BI Rate interest rate/Bank Indonesia Certificate/Deposits (Sharia Commercial Bank, Sharia Business Unit, Conventional Commercial Bank registered on the IDX, Bank Jabar Banten KC Rangkasbitung, Sharia Business Unit, BPRS in Indonesia, BNI, State Foreign Exchange Bank); (49) Sharia Compliance (Sharia Commercial Bank); (50) Government Retail Sukuk for the 2012-2015 period; (51) Corporate social responsibility; (52) Tax Amnesty (Sharia Commercial Banks and Sharia Business Units); and (53) Company size (Sharia Commercial Bank).

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Obstacles that Influence the Distribution & Management of Third Party Funds in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Based on several studies, there are 18 obstacles that influence the distribution and management of TPF in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Business and social functions (Sharia Commercial Bank); (2) Lack of public interest in saving (BMT Masalahah Besuk Agung Branch); (3) Lack of Human Resources/HR in marketing (BMT Masalahah Besuk Agung Branch); (4) Lack of marketing network (BMT Masalahah Besuk Agung Branch); (5) Issuance of Retail Sukuk (Sharia Commercial Bank); (6) Investment decisions (Sharia Commercial Banks); (7) Funding decisions (Sharia Commercial Bank); and (8) Profit Sharing (Sharia Commercial Bank); and (18) Moral Hazard (Sharia Commercial Banks).

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Third Party Funds in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Based on several studies, there are 37 influences caused by DPK on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Total assets (Conventional Commercial Bank, Sharia Commercial Bank, BPRS Jabal Nur Surabaya); (2) Operational Costs to Operational Income/BOPO (Commercial Banks listed on the IDX); (3) Base Lending Rate/BLR (National Private Banks and Persero registered on the IDX); (4) Debt Financing (Sharia Commercial Bank); (5) Hajj bailout funds (Bank Syariah Inonesia, Bank Muamalat Indonesia); (6) Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR (National Pension Savings Bank, Bank Mualamat Indonesia, Sharia Commercial Bank); (7) Intermediation function (BPR Malang City); (8) Share price (Commercial Banks listed on the IDX during the Covid-19 pandemic); (9) Company operational performance (during the Covid-19 pandemic, Badung Regency LPD, Tabanan Regency LPD, Conventional Commercial Banks registered on the IDX); (10) Financial performance (Conventional Commercial Banks listed on the IDX); (10) Consumer credit (Conventional Commercial Banks); (11) Investment credit; (12) Profit/income/margin/profit sharing (after tax Bank Syariah Bukopin, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Bank Syariah Commercial, BNI, Rural Bank in Lumajang, Bank OCBC NISP, BRI Unit Sirenja, Bank Jabar Syariah KC Bandung, Commercial Bank Conventional registered on the IDX, BNI Syariah, BUMN Commercial Bank, National Private Commercial Bank Foreign Exchange at Bank Indonesia, Bank UOB Indonesia KC Samarinda, Bank Mega Syariah, Bank Nusantara Parahyangan Sudirman Branch).

Next, namely: (13) Liquidity (Sharia Commercial Bank, Rural Bank, Pakraman Banyuning Gerogkak LPD, Ayunan Traditional Village LPD, Badung Regency, Bank

Sumsel Babel Jakabaring Palembang, Bank Mandiri, BNI, BCA); (14) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR (Commercial Banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, Bank BUMN Persero); (15) Community welfare (Sharia Commercial Bank); (16) Macroeconomics (National Private Commercial Bank of East Java Province); (17) Net Profit Margin/NPM (BTN); (18) Non Performing Loans/NPL (Conventional Commercial Banks); (19) Net Interest Margin/NIM (Regional Government Bank); (20) Non Performing Financing/NPF (Islamic Banks in Indonesia and Malaysia); (21) Company value (Sharia Commercial Bank); (22) Operations (BUMN Banks registered on the IDX); (23) Market share (Sharia Commercial Bank); (24) Murabahah, Mudharabah, Musyarakah, profit sharing, Natural Uncertainty Contract/NUC, MSME financing (BUMN Bank, Al-Yaqin BPRS, BPRS in Indonesia, BPRS in Riau Province, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Conventional Commercial Bank & Sharia Commercial Bank registered with BEI & OJK, BRI Syariah KC Gubeng Surabaya, Bank Syariah Bukopin, Sharia Business Unit); (25) Placement of funds with Bank Indonesia (Sharia Commercial Bank); (26) Issuance of Indonesia Government Securities/IGS; (27) Increasing social responsibility (Sharia Commercial Banks).

Next, namely: (28) Distribution/provision/growth of credit/working capital/KUR People's Business Credit (Conventional Commercial Banks/BUMN registered on the IDX, Non-Foreign Exchange Sharia Commercial Banks, investment credit from Regional Government Banks, North Maluku Bank, BRI KC Majalaya Unit Dayeuhkolot, BRI Unit Lalabata Rilau Soppeng Regency, BRI in Indonesia, Conventional Commercial Banks registered on the IDX, BPD during the Covid-19 pandemic, BPD in Indonesia, Bank Nagari, UMKM BPR Sukawati Pancakanti, Bank Central Asia, Bank Mandiri, Bank Central Sulutgo Manado, BPD West Java Tbk. KCP Ciparay, BPD Bali, BPR in Bantul Regency, BPR in Semarang City, BPR Bandung Kidul, BPR in Indonesia, Foreign Banks that Go Public, Village Credit Institutions/LPDs in Kediri District, Tabanan Regency, LPD Pakraman Pamaron Village, LPD Bandung Regency, LPD Denpasar City, BTN KC Makassar period May-June 2019, BPR Kredit Mandiri Jabar, Bank Jabar Banten KC Cimahi, BPR in Indonesia, Bank Mandiri KC Makassar on working capital, BPR in Indonesia, Bank Riau Kepri KC Selatpanjang, BMT Muda East Java, Bank Central Asia, BPD Kaltimara Samarinda, BPRS Bakti Makmur Indah, BPR Christa Jaya Perdana, BPR Mitra Riau, BCA, BPR East Java KC Batu, Commercial Banks in South Sulawesi, Sharia Commercial Banks in West Sumatra, BNI, Tanah Abang Sharia Market Traders Cooperative, Central Jakarta, BPRS Lantabur Jombang, Commercial Banks in Riau); (29) Credit requests (Conventional Commercial Banks); (30) Economic growth in Indonesia.

Next, namely: (31) Profitability/Return On Assets/Return On Equity (BRI, National Private Commercial Bank for Foreign Exchange registered on the IDX, Bank Mandiri, BTN, Bank Nasional Indonesia, Bank Syariah Bukopin, Bank Central Asia, BPR in Jakarta, BPR in Tangerang, BPRS Al Salaam Amal Salman, BPRS in Indonesia, BPRS in Semarang City, BPRS Al Ihsan, Rural Bank Nur Abadi Singaraja, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Covid-19 pandemic period, BRIS KCP Pati Central Java, Bank BUMN, BPD Bali, BPD in Indonesia, Sharia Foreign Exchange Commercial Bank, Bank Aceh, KJKS BMT in Tanah Datar, Village Credit Institution/LPD Pakraman Ubud Village, LPD Jimbaran Traditional Village, LPD Badung Regency, LPD Denpasar City, LPD Mengwi District, BPR Suryajaya Ubud, Bank Mega Tbk., Bank Jabar Banten, Sharia Commercial Bank registered with OJK, Commercial Bank registered with BEI, Bank Mega Syariah, Bank Panin Dubai Syariah, Non-Bank LKS in Tulungagung and Blitar, Foreign Banks in Indonesia, BPR in Jakarta); (32) Best

product (BRI Syariah uses Analytic Hierachy Process/AHP); (33) Return On Investment/ROI (BPR PK Balongan Indramayu); (34) Profitability (Bank Mandiri, BNI, BCA); (35) Sustainable Development Goals/SDGs; (36) Governance (Sharia Commercial Banks registered with the OJK use the Restricted Profit Sharing Investment Account/RPSIA approach); and (37) Electronic money/E-Money transactions in Indonesia.

Conclusion and Suggestions

Based on the results of the discussion above, the conclusions are as follows:

- Number of research publications regarding Third Party Funds in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2007 to 2022, with a total publication of 628 research articles.
- The affiliates/institutions that publish the most research results are JIMAT (Scientific Journal of Accounting Students) Undiksha and the FEB Student Scientific Journal, each with 20 articles published.
- The researchers who were most productive in publishing research results were Ami Nullah Marlis Tanjung and Hasbi Assidiki Mauluddi with a total of 3 journal article publications.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding Third Party Funds are divided into 6 clusters and 190 topics. Cluster 1 in red consists of 71 topics. Cluster 2 in green consists of 51 topics. The 3 dark blue clusters consist of 40 topics. Cluster 4 in yellow consists of 20 topics. The 5 purple clusters consist of 4 topics. The 6 light blue clusters consist of 4 topics.
- Based on the Library Research, there are five main research themes surrounding Third Party Fund research in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: (1) Third Party Fund growth strategies, there are 6 topics; (2) Public interest, recording, legal basis and policy for Third Party Funds; (3) Factors influencing the collection of Third Party Funds, there are 53 topics; (4) There are 18 obstacles affecting the distribution & management of Third Party Funds; and (5) The Influence of Third Party Funds, there are 37 topics.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j->

ebis.v7i1.3895

- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Library Research Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per

- Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Kompetensi (Competence: Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick

ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Library Research. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi

Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>

Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>

Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>

Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>

Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>

Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>

Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>

Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>